

CUTTING OF CFRP WITH SINGLE EDGE TOOLS

Aksel KOPLEV

*Risø National Laboratory, Metallurgy Department
Postbox 49, DK 4000 Roskilde, Denmark*

The cutting process in the machining of carbon fibre-reinforced plastics (cfrp) has been investigated. Cutting experiments have been carried out on unidirectional cfrp. The experiments involved orthogonal cutting of cfrp with a shaping machine and a 'quick-stop' machine.

A new method called 'macrochip' has been developed for ease of handling and investigation of the very small chips. The present work shows that the cutting process consists of a series of fractures, each releasing a small chip. This work presents a qualitative model for cutting parallel to the fibres, and discusses the thermodynamical relationships of the cutting process.

INTRODUCTION

This paper will discuss the mechanism of cutting unidirectional cfrp (carbon fibre-reinforced plastics) with single edge tools. The main purpose is to create a basis for improving the cutting quality, and for understanding the cutting process.

Most of the cfrp components which are produced today are fabricated by auto-clave moulding, compression moulding or filament winding. All these processes produce parts in their final shape. The volume of machining required is low and restricted to critical spots on the components, such as holes for joints or edges where the components should fit other parts of the construction.

Only a few works on cutting cfrp have been published. Friend et. al. [1] compared different machining methods. From their paper it can be concluded that the economy of single edge tools is good, but the geometrical performance and the overall quality is low. They did not find any clear difference in the strength of composites machined by conventional drilling, diamond cutting or ultrasonic drilling. Rujikietgumjorn [2] and Johansson et Mattila [3] each investigated the drilling of cfrp with cemented carbide-tipped twist drills. Rujikietgumjorn drilled in a hybrid cfrp/titanium composite (12.7 mm cfrp plus 7.6 mm Ti). The drills lasted for only a few holes after which they broke-down. A probable reason for the quick breakdown is the severe heat buildup which was found at the tool edge. Johansson et Mattila drilled 6-mm holes with a speed of 1.5 m/s. They found a tool life corresponding to the length of 1 m of hole, before the tool was worn out.

The theory of machining fibre-reinforced materials is not very well established, although Everstine et Rogers [4] published a work on this topic. Unfortunately they considered the case of large deformations of an 'ideal' fibre-reinforced composite. It will be shown later that such large deformations do not occur when machining cfrp.

THE EXPERIMENTS, MACHINING METHODS

The experiments were carried out using a simplified orthogonal process characterized by a well-defined geometry. This reduces the number of independent parameters to be considered. Fig. 1 shows the nomenclature for the orthogonal process. The experiments were done on unidirectional cfrp, in two directions relating to the fibres, parallel and perpendicular; they are also shown in Fig. 1.

Two devices were applied for the experiments: An instrumented shaping machine was used to investigate the workpiece surface together with the chips and also for measurements of the cutting force. A 'quick-stop' machine was used to investigate details of the process near the tool-tip and in front of it. The experiments on the 'quick-stop' machine gave also additional information regarding the workpiece surface and chips. The 'quick-stop' machine is a specially designed device [5]. During the experiment the cutting takes place on the flank of the plate-shaped specimen. At the end of the experiment the cutting process is stopped very quickly: The tool is decelerated from full speed (1.5 m/s) to zero in approx. 20 μ s. In this time the tool moves approx. 14 μ m. Table 1 gives details of the workpiece materials and cutting data for both the shaping experiments and the 'quick-stop' experiments.

Figure 1 Nomenclature of the orthogonal cutting process and definition of cutting directions. α : Rake angle, β : Relief angle, t : Chip thickness (= Cutting depth), v : Cutting velocity, w : Specimen and cutting width, A: Parallel cutting direction, B: Perpendicular cutting direction.

		Shaping Experiments	'Quick-stop' Experiments
Material	Type	Pultruded bar with approx. 65 vol % carbon and 35 vol % epoxy (fibre: Grafil A, epoxy: unknown)	Unidirectional cfrp made from prepreg. 61 vol % carbon and 39 vol % epoxy (fibre: Toraca T300, epoxy: Toray no 3120)
	Specimen	25 mm x 25 mm x 3.5 mm	50 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm
Tool	Material	High speed steel (Fagersta WKE 45)	Cemented carbide
	Rake angle	0 degree	0 degree
	Relief angle	15 degree	15 degree
Cutting data	Cut. depth	0.05 mm, 0.1 mm and 0.2 mm	0.05 mm - 0.2 mm
	Velocity	0.24 m/s and 0.8 m/s	1.5 m/s
	Width	3.5 mm	2 mm
	Direction	Parallel and perpendicular	Parallel and perpendicular

Table 1 Overview of workpiece materials, tools and cutting data.

THE MACROCHIP METHOD

Useful information on the cutting process has been obtained from the chips, but their very small size makes them difficult to handle and study. A solution to the problems is the so-called 'macrochip' preparation method. This method assembles a number of chips into a larger unit; the 'macrochip' is easy to handle and useable for investigation by SEM or optical microscopy. The 'macrochips' are produced by a three-step procedure:

- a: The workpiece surface is coated with a thin layer of rubber-based adhesive, which is allowed to dry.
- b: The machining takes place; after this all the chips stick to the adhesive.
- c: The chips on the adhesive are transferred to a suitable support for later investigation.

The final macrochip consists of the chips and the adhesive plus a necessary support; they are bonded to a small glass plate by a piece of double-coated adhesive tape. Furthermore, the macrochip is stretched to enable the individual chips to be more easily seen. Fig. 2a is a schematic diagram showing the structure of the macrochip. The thickness of the adhesive ranges from 0.03 mm to 0.09 mm. Fig. 2b is a macrochip seen from above; the cutting was done in the parallel direction.

Figure 2 (a) Schematic diagram of macrochip. (b) Macrochip seen from above; cutting data: $v = 0.24$ m/s, $t = 0.1$ mm; cutting direction: parallel.

Although the macrochip method is developed for use when machining cfrp, it may be useful on other brittle materials which form short chips, e.g. plastics or brass, but it is limited to discontinuous processes.

THE MACHINED SURFACE

The surface obtained when machining cfrp depends especially on the machining direction regarding the fibres. Machining in the parallel direction creates rather fine surfaces with a roughness of $1.7 - 4.7 \mu\text{m}$ Cla. (the roughness varies with the process parameters). Fig. 3 shows two cross-sections of specimens machined in the parallel direction.

Figure 3 Cross-sections of specimens. (a) Machined surface of pultruded bar, and (b) machined surface of a plate made from prepreg.

The outermost one or two fibres, especially on the prepreg specimens, are fractured in small pieces between 8 and 40 μm in length. Those pieces are explained in the following way: As the cutting tool moves across the specimen, it presses down on the surface. The pressure and the cutting movement create a friction force, which stretches the fibres on the surface. The pull in the fibres is large enough to fracture them.

Machining in the perpendicular direction creates surfaces with a greater roughness of between 8.5 and 23.5 μm Cla. The large surface roughness is a disadvantage in that it is then very difficult to maintain narrow tolerances. Furthermore, there is a layer between 5 and 15 μm thick of disturbed material on the surface where both matrix material and small pieces of fibre are present. There is an area with a depth of between 90 and 150 μm with cracks below the surface, some of which go obliquely from the surface down into the specimen. Others go parallel with the surface at a certain depth. This layer below the surface has two main drawbacks: The cracks lower the strength of the surface because the area between the cracks could easily be broken off when stressed. There is also a high risk of moisture absorption, which becomes especially serious if the moisture later penetrates further into the composite via the fibre-matrix interface. Fig. 4 is a micrograph of a surface machined perpendicular to the fibres.

Figure 4 Micrograph of surface machined in the perpendicular direction.

THE CHIPS

Machining cfrp creates many small chips. The chips are small pieces of composite broken off from the specimen. The pieces are relatively undisturbed during the cutting process; most of the fibres in the chips are whole. As expected there is no sign of plastic deformation of the chips, because both the matrix and the fibres are considered as brittle. Fig. 5a is a SEM micrograph of two individual chips. The machining was done in the parallel direction and it is seen that only a few of the fibres in the chips are fractured. Fig. 5b is another SEM micrograph; this one shows chips obtained when machining in the perpendicular direction. On this micrograph also, most of the fibres are whole. Like the machined specimen surfaces, those of the chips have a thin layer of destroyed composite; this layer is seen in Fig. 5b, but not in 5a, because it is removed purposely so that the chips can be seen.

Figure 5 SEM micrographs of chips. (a) From machining done in the perpendicular direction, the chips are seen at an angle ($V = 0.24$ m/s, $t = 0.1$ mm). (b) From machining done in the parallel direction, the chips are seen from above ($V = 0.24$ m/s, $t = 0.05$ mm).

CONDITIONS AT THE TOOL-TIP

A 'quick-stop' machine was used to evaluate the conditions of the cutting process near the tool-tip. Machining in the perpendicular direction results in a sharp notch at the point where the tool was stopped. No cracks were found in front of the notch where the tool was stopped. This indicates that the cracks in the specimen on the machined part of the surface are created below the tool, not in front of it.

Machining in the parallel direction provides a rather sharp notch also (see Fig. 6b) but two matters should be noticed: First the fibres in front of the tool position are slightly bent. This is in contrast to the observations found when investigating the chips. The other matter to observe is the cracks in front of the notch. This one is considered as the start of the next chip

Figure 6 Cross-section of specimens after 'quick-stop' experiments. (a) From machining in the perpendicular direction. (b) From machining in the parallel direction. $V = 1.5$ m/s.

DISCUSSION

A qualitative model of the cutting in the parallel direction must consider the following: The chip creation process includes crack production parallel to the cutting direction, a bending of the fibres in front of the tool and a fracture perpendicular to the fibre direction which releases the chip from the specimen. Fig. 7 is a sketch of the cutting process; it includes the above-mentioned phenomena.

A model of the cutting in the perpendicular direction must consider the cracks below the tool, and include a chip releasing mechanism.

In a later work a quantitative analysis of the cutting process will be published.

Figure 7 Sketch of the parallel cutting process.

The energy used when cutting cfrp may be divided into:

- a: The energy for the creating and releasing of the chips, and
- b: The energy used for the friction between the tool and specimen surface.

The energy is lost during the process and causes heat build-up, the heat build-up will take place at three locations:

- i: In the chips,
- ii: In the specimen, and
- iii: In the tool.

An investigation of other fibre composites, e.g. glass/epoxy [6] showed that 90% of the heat was conducted to the tool. This heat build-up causes high temperatures at the tool-tip, and reduces the wear resistance of the tool. The friction can be reduced using a large relief angle; 15 degrees has been used in the present work.

CONCLUSIONS

The macrochip method is a useful preparation method for investigation of the cutting process on cfrp.

The cutting mechanism should be considered with respect to the fibre direction. It is a fracture process where the cutting is carried out as a series of brittle fractures. Only negligible plastic deformation is present.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author wishes to thank the Metallurgy Department, Risø National Laboratory and the Division of Mechanical Processing of Materials at the Technical University of Denmark for financing the project and for providing the experimental equipment.

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